

TOOLPATH OPTIMIZATION OF POLYMER COMPOSITE ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING (AM) PRINTED MOLD TO IMPROVE PERFORMANCE FOR COMPRESSION MOLDING APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the optimization of toolpaths for short fiber polymer composite additive manufacturing (AM) printed molds in compression molding applications, an emerging trend driven by advancements in 3D printing technology. AM printed molds offer reduced tooling costs and greater design flexibility, particularly for prototyping and low-volume production. The proposed optimization approach evaluates mold performance using two key metrics: deformation and shape accuracy. Multiple toolpaths are generated, and finite element (FE) simulations capture fiber orientation and material properties, which are then integrated into a mechanical performance model. Shape accuracy is assessed by comparing the deformed mold shape with the original using surface normals as a descriptor. The analysis identifies the toolpath that delivers the best overall performance, establishing it as the most suitable option for achieving optimal mold characteristics in compression molding applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

The adoption of additive manufacturing (AM) using short fiber polymer composites for producing molds has gained traction, particularly in the context of molding applications [1, 2]. This emerging trend is driven by advancements in 3D printing technology, which offers significant advantages over traditional mold production methods. Notably, AM printed molds provide reduced tooling costs and greater design flexibility, making them ideal for prototyping and low-volume production scenarios [3, 4].

A critical aspect of additive manufacturing is the planning of the printing path, also known as the toolpath. The toolpath plays a pivotal role in determining the quality of the mold surface and its subsequent performance during use [5-7]. In this study, a novel approach to optimize toolpaths is

proposed with the aim of enhancing the performance of AM printed molds specifically designed for compression molding applications.

The optimization strategy focuses on evaluating mold performance through two essential metrics: deformation and shape accuracy. The process begins with generating multiple toolpaths for a chosen AM mold geometry and material. For each generated toolpath, Finite Element (FE)-based simulations were conducted to investigate the resulting fiber orientation and material properties throughout the mold structure. These properties were then integrated into a mechanical performance model, enabling to assess the mold's deformation under compression loading conditions.

In addition to deformation, shape accuracy was assessed by comparing the deformed mold shape to its original, as-printed form. This evaluation was accomplished using surface normals as shape descriptors, which allowed to analyze the orientation of the mold surface at various points and quantify any shape deviations.

After analyzing the deformation and shape accuracy metrics for all considered toolpaths, the toolpath that offered the best overall mold performance was identified. This optimized toolpath was determined to be most appropriate for achieving the desired characteristics of molds used in compression molding applications.

Through this work, the aim was to contribute to the field of additive manufacturing by providing a systematic approach for toolpath optimization, ultimately enhancing the efficacy of AM printed molds.

2 MATERIAL, GEOMETRY AND DISCRETIZATION

The geometry of the mold considered for the present task was a double dome. The printed double dome mold consisted of a thicker base (Fig. 1) for the purpose of maintaining a continuous toolpath during the print, however the excess material at the base is later removed or machined for obtaining the actual mold. Thus, the printed mold geometry was considered for the AM process simulation while the actual mold geometry was considered for the performance simulation.

Figure 1: Illustration of the printed mold (left) and the actual mold (right) used for performance analysis.

20wt% CF/PLA was the chosen material for the numerical evaluation of the double dome structure. The double dome printed geometry was discretized for the AM simulation (Fig. 2). Accordingly, the element size for the discretization was chosen equal to the bead dimensions, with the bead height equating to the layer thickness. The same mesh was used further for the performance analysis, except that the elements making up the excess material at the base of the mold were removed.

Figure 2: Discretization of printable mold, element size ($\sim 5\text{mm}$) chosen equal to the bead height, overall mold dimensions, $L = \sim 550\text{mm}$, $W = \sim 300\text{mm}$, printed height $H = 200\text{mm}$, actual mold height $H' = 150\text{mm}$.

The material properties of the CF/PLA composite were determined using the MCQ chopped software [8]. Accordingly, the constituent material properties of CF (Table 1) and PLA (Table 2), along with the fiber orientation distribution for a bead thickness of 5mm (Table 3) were provided as input to the micromechanical model. The fiber orientation distribution was defined by assuming a paper-ply based approach, however a more accurate method of defining fiber orientation distribution in case of short-fiber reinforced composites is by defining a fiber orientation tensor.

Table 1: Properties of the PLA matrix required to perform micromechanical simulations.

Matrix Property		PLA
<i>Elastic Modulus (E)</i>	[GPa]	3.6
<i>Poisson's Ratio (ν)</i>	–	0.3
<i>Tensile Strength</i>	[MPa]	25
<i>Compressive Strength</i>	[MPa]	53
<i>Shear Strength</i>	[MPa]	20.25
<i>Density (ρ)</i>	[kg/m ³]	1240

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the CF fibers.

Property		CF
ρ	[kg/m ³]	1790
E_{11}	[GPa]	221.8
E_{22}	[GPa]	18.86
E_{33}	[GPa]	18.86
G_{12}	[GPa]	58.81
G_{23}	[GPa]	6.96
G_{13}	[GPa]	6.96
ν_{12}	–	0.2218
ν_{23}	–	0.3548
ν_{13}	–	0.3548
Tensile S11T	[MPa]	3432
Compressive S11C	[MPa]	2416
Shear S12	[MPa]	150.0

Table 3: Fiber orientation distribution for CF/PLA composite bead with a thickness of 5 mm.

Ply Thickness (mm)	Normalized thickness	Orientation tensor components (°)	Orientation tensor components
1.75	0.35	0	1.0
0.25	0.40	45	0.5
1.00	0.60	90	0.0
0.25	0.65	45	0.5
1.75	1.00	0	1.0

Additionally, the fiber properties including an average fiber length of $180\mu\text{m}$, fiber diameter of $9\mu\text{m}$, and void fraction of 20% were assumed. The mechanical properties of CF/PLA were obtained as output from the model (Table 4). These properties were then imported into the input file of the performance analysis.

Table 4: Mechanical properties of CF/PLA composite.

Property		CF/PLA
P	[kg/m^3]	1066
E_{11}	[GPa]	15.61
E_{22}	[GPa]	6.852
E_{33}	[GPa]	3.249
G_{12}	[GPa]	1.569
G_{23}	[GPa]	1.168
G_{13}	[GPa]	1.167
ν_{12}	–	0.167
ν_{23}	–	0.352
ν_{13}	–	0.326
Tensile S11T	[MPa]	111.6
Shear S12	[MPa]	22.14

3 TOOLPATH AND BUILD ORIENTATION

Next, three cases of AM printing consisting of different combinations of build orientation and toolpath were selected for evaluation. The three cases were termed H0, H90 and V90 where ‘H’ or ‘V’ referred to a horizontal or vertical build orientation and ‘0’ or ‘90’ referred to the toolpath in x or y direction (Fig. 3). Note that each figure was enlarged to show the toolpath representing the material orientation.

Figure 3: Printed mold configurations (a) H0, (b) H90, and (c) V90 used for performance evaluation.

The first step in the evaluation of the above cases was the determination of their elemental material orientation. Due to the tortuous nature of the toolpath used for the AM process, the material coordinates change as a function of the toolpath. This was captured in the AM process simulation such as each element was assigned to a local coordinate system that defined the material deposition

direction. Further, the elements of the discretized geometry that intersected the toolpath were activated during the process simulation. Only those active elements were assigned the local coordinates in the process simulation. Thus, for each of the three cases, an AMs process simulation was performed to determine the active elements in the model and to obtain their local coordinates.

In each of the cases, more than 99% of the elements were determined to be active and their local coordinates were extracted in a text file using a python script. This data was then incorporated into the input file for the performance analysis. The material orientation for the three cases can be seen in (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Elemental Material orientation (1-2-3 axes) obtained from the AM process simulation for (a) H0, (b) H90, and (c) V90 cases, plotted only for few elements on the wireframe geometry of the actual mold.

4 PERFORMANCE MODEL

In order to evaluate the performance of the mold, two metrics were used including deformation and shape accuracy. For evaluation of the mold deformation consisting of different toolpaths, a performance model was setup using Abaqus Standard. The performance model was set up by defining the displacement BCs and loading condition (Fig. 5). A non-linear static analysis was performed to evaluate the structural performance of the three cases.

Figure 5: Displacement BCs and loading conditions for the performance analysis of double dome structure (a) Front view shows hydrostatic pressure loading and fixed bottom face, (b) Top view shows locations used to fix the structure.

Shape accuracy was evaluated by comparing the mold's deformed shape to its original, as-printed form. This was done by using surface normals as a shape descriptor. The surface normal descriptor compared the orientation of the mold surface at each point to assess shape deviation. The concept of surface deviation is illustrated in (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Surface deviation angle calculated from the vertex normal to the original and deformed mold surfaces.

The surface deviation angle θ_i is calculated at a vertex/node on the surface as follows:

$$\theta_i = \cos^{-1}(\hat{a}_i \cdot \hat{b}_i), \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

Where \hat{a}_i, \hat{b}_i are the unit normal vectors to the original and deformed surfaces, respectively, at a vertex i , and n is the number of vertices/nodes on the surface. Further, the variance of the surface deviation angles for the mold surface was calculated as:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum(\theta_i - \bar{\theta})}{n} \quad (2)$$

Where $\bar{\theta}$ is the mean surface deviation. Accordingly, the surface deviation data including the deviation angles, their maximum and minimum magnitudes, and the average and variance were determined for all three cases under study.

5 RESULTS

The results of the performance analyses provided insights into 1) the structural integrity of the AM mold and 2) the quality of part manufactured using the mold through compression molding. The key observations from the predicted stress and deformation results are presented here. The von Mises stress contour plots for the three cases can be observed in (Fig. 7). The scale of the contour plot was set at a maximum of 45MPa and a minimum of 0MPa.

Figure 7: Von Mises stress contour plots for (a) H0, (b) H90, and (c) V90 cases, scale set to a Max = 45 MPa and Min = 0 MPa.

It was observed that the average stress magnitudes for all cases were similar with certain disparity visible on the top face. The stress contours were expected to be similar because the loading condition was pressure-based. Thus, the deformation results were determined to be more valuable for the purpose of comparison. The deformation magnitude for the considered cases can be seen in (Fig. 8). The maximum deformation magnitudes for H0, H90 and V90 cases were 1.056mm, 1.067mm and 0.441mm respectively. Unlike cases H0, and H90, V90 case has material axis 1 that is the fiber axis in the loading direction, thus provided higher stiffness, resulting in lower deformation by >50.

Figure 8: Deformation magnitude contour plots for (a) H0, (b) H90, and (c) V90 cases, scale set to Max = 1.1 mm and Min = 0.0 mm.

Considering deformation magnitude as the criterion for performance evaluation of the AM mold, considerable improvement was achieved with V0 case (>50%) compared to the H0 and H90 cases. Thus, it would be logical to determine V90 toolpath as the optimum from a performance perspective. However, it was recognized that an equally important criterion for evaluation of the optimum toolpath was the quality of part manufactured using the mold via compression molding. In the present instance, the part quality was defined by surface deviation of the deformed mold relative to the original mold surface.

Accordingly, the surface deviation data including the deviation angles, their maximum and minimum magnitudes, and the average and variance were determined for all three cases under study. The deviation or the error values are provided in (Table 5). The maximum deviation and variance metrics were considered significant for the part quality. Thus, the H90 toolpath case was determined the optimum case in terms of the part quality.

Table 5: Surface deviation values used as error metric to choose the optimum toolpath.

Error metric	Case H0	Case H90	Case V90
Max deviation (°)	3.137	2.591	4.197
Min deviation (°)	0.002	0.002	0.001
Avg deviation (°)	0.211	0.210	0.122
Variance of deviation	0.034	0.027	0.059
Optimum ranking	Next to optimum	Optimum	Second next to optimum

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study focused on toolpath optimization for an additive manufacturing (AM) printed mold to enhance its molding performance, evaluated through mold deformation and shape accuracy metrics. Three toolpaths including H0, H90, and V90 were assessed using finite element (FE) simulations and statistical analysis. The results indicated that the V90 toolpath was optimal for compression molding applications due to its lowest mold deformation, attributable to favorable fiber alignment in the loading direction that enhanced material stiffness. However, shape accuracy analysis revealed that the V90 case exhibited the highest maximum deviation and variance from the original mold shape. In contrast, the H90 toolpath demonstrated the lowest deviation and variance, indicating superior shape accuracy, albeit with slightly higher mold deformation than the V90. Therefore, considering the trade-offs between mold deformation and shape accuracy, the H90 toolpath is recommended as the optimal choice.

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APPENDIX

Figure A1. Picture of the AM printed mold on a support (left) and machined to the required dimensions for compression molding application (right)